

EFFECT OF WETTABILITY ON IMPREGNATION PROCESS OF VISCOUS FLUID TO WOVEN FIBER BUNDLES

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1. Introduction

Fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) is a material with high strength and rigidity. However, high manufacturing costs have become a problem.

Resin transfer molding (RTM) and vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) method that have no cost emerge.

RTM methods

Pros : low cost
 Cons : low strength

Since the applied pressure is small, the air in the fiber cannot be completely removed, and residual bubbles (voids) are generated. Stress concentration in the voids leads to a decrease in strength.

Simulate void formation applying Darcy's law in consideration of wettability¹.

Show the correlation between the void formation and the resin impregnation².

Objective

The effects of wettability on the three-dimensional behaviors of the viscous liquid and on the formation processes of microvoids in fiber bundles are investigated.

$$Ca = \frac{\mu U}{\sigma} \quad Ca' = \frac{\mu U}{\sigma \cos \theta}$$

μ [kg/m·s] : Viscosity
 U [m/s] : Flow velocity
 σ [N/m] : Surface tension
 θ [°] : Contact angle

2. Calculation model and condition

	Liquid (blue)	Gas (green)
Density (kg/m ³)	1100	1.2
Kinematic viscosity (mm ² /s)	36.36 - 90.91	15
Surface tension (mN/m)	21	0
Initial velocity (mm/s)	10	0
Particle diameter (mm)	0.57	0.57
Contact angle (fiber) (°)	0 - 60	-
Contact angle (substrate) (°)	0	-

3. Calculation method

Moving particle semi-implicit method

$$\text{Continuity Equation} : \frac{D\rho}{Dt} = 0$$

$$\text{N-S Equation} : \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{g} + \frac{1}{\rho} \sigma \kappa \delta \mathbf{n}$$

Software	Particle works 6.1
Calculation method	Moving particle semi-implicit
Surface tension	CSF model
Influence radius	3.1r
Time step	0.00005 (s)

4. Results and Discussion

The pressure is high near the inlet, and is low between and in the fiber bundles.

It can be seen that not all liquid particles passing through a channel follow the same trajectory.

This is a typical example that the woven fiber bundles cause a three-dimensional complex impregnation within the mold.

The final microvoid rate increases as θ_f and ν increase.

It is also found that the effect of the viscosity is smaller under larger θ_f than 0° , i.e., the influence of θ_f is greater than ν .

Under the present calculation conditions, the formation of microvoids can be suppressed when the viscosity is small and the wettability is good.

5. Conclusion

We realize the process of viscous fluid impregnation into woven fiber bundles by three-dimensional numerical calculation with MPS method. It is indicated a correlation between the microvoid formation and the impregnation process in terms of Ca and Ca' . It is indicated that the influence of the contact angle is underestimated in the definition of Ca' .

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7. Reference

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